

Bioactive metabolites from *Valeriana* genera[†]

C. S. Mathela* and C. S. Chanotiya^a

Department of Chemistry, Kumaun University, Nainital-263 002, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : mathelacs@gmail.com

^aCSIR-Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, CSIR-CIMAP, Post CIMAP, Lucknow-226 015, Uttar Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 24 October 2011, accepted 26 October 2011

Abstract : *Valeriana* species (Valerianaceae) with cosmopolitan distribution are the source of important phytomedicines for curing nervous unrest, emotional troubles (as tranquilizer/sedative), epilepsy and insanity. Valerian continues to be a safe sedative/hypnotic choice for patients with mild to moderate insomnia. *Valeriana* species possess variety of bioactive sesquiterpenoids flavour chemicals and valepotriates possessing unique structural features. The activity of Valerian herbs is largely due to the valepotriates but the results show the sesquiterpenoids as being equally effective. Some valepotriates exhibit significant cytotoxic activity. Recent reports have indicated the existence of chemically distinct chemotypes within certain *Valeriana* consequently affecting their bioactivity. Present communication reviews recent work on Himalayan *Valeriana* viz., *V. wallichii* DC. (*V. jatamansi*), *V. himalayana* (*V. dioica* L.), *V. pyrolaefolia* Decne, *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii* and *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* (Wt. C.B.).

Keywords : *Valeriana*, Valerian, *V. wallichii* DC. (*V. jatamansi*), *V. himalayana* (*V. dioica* L.), *V. pyrolaefolia*, *V. mussooriensis*, *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii*, *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* (Wt. C.B.).

1. Introduction

The genus *Valeriana* with about 200 species belongs to the family Valerianaceae and has global distribution. The roots and rhizomes of *Valeriana* species are usually aromatic. *Valeriana officinalis* L. is part of British and European Pharmacopeias. The Japanese Valerian drug is prepared from *Valeriana faurie*. In China, Valerian drugs are part of traditional medicines for hypnotic, tranquilizer and antiviral activities^{1,2}. The Indian Valerian has long been used in Ayurveda (Charak Samhita and Susruta) and Unani systems of medicine which describe its use in obesity, skin disease, insanity, epilepsy and snake poisoning^{3,4}. The crude drugs from roots/ rhizomes and valerian derived phytomedicines are used as mild sedatives in pharmaceutical industry. The roots/rhizome parts are highly aromatic and the *Valeriana* essential oil is also in great demand for flavour and pharmaceutical preparations. In recent years, a number of Indian Himalayan *Valeriana* species have been screened for chemical constituents⁵⁻¹². These have been found to possess a variety of

compounds including maaliol, patchouli alcohol, 8-acetoxypatchouli alcohol, valeranone, α -kessyl acetate, valeracetate, valerenic acid and its derivatives. The second most important group is a series of non-glycosidic bicyclic iridoid epoxy-triesters known as valepotriates (valtrate, isovaltrate, acevaltrate, didrovaltrate and their homologues) which have restricted occurrence in Valerianaceae and display unique structural features not encountered in other iridoids. The presence of a large number of small group of acylated iridoids, associated with the sedative activity of valerian preparations have been isolated and reported from *Valeriana wallichii* syn. (*V. jatamansi*) and its tissue culture¹³⁻¹⁹. Besides, the sedative activity of valepotriates, cytotoxicity^{14,20} has also been reported.

Keeping the global interest in the valerian drug, their chemical diversity and existence of the chemotypes within species in view, the recent phytochemical and bioactivity work specially in the Indian Valerian is being reviewed.

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Distribution of Indian Valerian

1.1. General distribution

North western Himalaya represents a rich biodiversity. *Valeriana*, the major genus in the family Valerianaceae, is characterized by perennials that have three stamens without spurs on the slightly swollen base of the corolla, with a short and often strong-smelling root stalk. Strachey reported in 1918 the occurrence of five *Valeriana* species, *V. dioica* L., *V. pyrolaefolia*, *V. stracheyi*, *V. wallichii* DC. and *V. hardwickii*, at elevations ranging from 1500 ± 4300 m²¹. A thorough re-investigation of the morphology, distribution, and biodiversity of the Indian Valerianaceae showed a total of 16 species/subspecies, of which six, namely *V. wallichii* DC. (*V. jatamansi*), *V. himalayana* (*V. dioica* L.), *V. pyrolaefolia* Decne, *V. mussooriensis*, *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii*, and *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* (Wt. C.B.) occur in Uttarakhand, Himalaya²². Indian Valerian, *V. wallichii* DC., has been used as an ingredient in Indian herbal medicines, and as a substitute of the European *V. officinalis*. Ancient Indian Ayurvedic and Unani literature describe the medicinal properties of Tagar (*V. wallichii*) for curing obesity, nervous disorders, epilepsy, insanity, snake poisoning, eye trouble, and skin disease. Today, *Valeriana* is still a highly respected herb described in many pharmacopoeia monographs. Charak Samhita, an ancient Indian medical text, describes two forms of *V. wallichii* distinguishable in the field alone⁴. Ved Prakash²² also describes it as variable in general size of plants, but with no specific difference in other plant characters. Thus, though used extensively since ancient times, *V. wallichii* has not been reported earlier to have subspecies or chemotypes. *V. wallichii* DC. has now been shown to exist chemically as three distinct chemotypes. *V. wallichii* DC. grows wild in the temperate Himalaya at 1500–3000 m.

V. pyrolaefolia Decne (Valerianaceae), a less explored species, is sub-succulent herb 5–25 cm tall, sparsely pubescent with long, slender root fibers descending from thick rhizomes, occurring in the temperate Himalaya in an altitude of 2000–4500 m, but is not as common as *V. wallichii* DC.^{21,22}. Two varieties of *V. hardwickii*, viz. *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii* and *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* and *V. dioica* reported in Himalayan region were collected by us.

2. Bioactive chemical compounds in *Valeriana*

2.1. Terpenoids

In an effort to determine the chemical diversity of the *Valeriana* genera of the Northwestern Himalaya, *V. wallichii* DC., *V. himalayana* (syn. *V. dioica*), *V. pyrolaefolia* Decne, and *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* and *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii* were screened for their terpenoid compositions.

We conclude that *V. wallichii* DC. includes three stable chemotypes, with no mixed population, chemotype-I being characterized by the presence of maaliol (1) and chemotype-II having patchouli alcohol (2) and 8-acetoxypatchouli alcohol (3) and kanokonyl acetate⁹ (4) in chemotype-III as major compounds. *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* was also found to exist as two independent chemotypes. Here, chemotype-I is characterized by α -kessyl acetate (5), valeracetate (6), and 8-epikessyl glycol diacetate (7), whereas the chemotype-II species contain maaliol (1) and kessanyl acetate (8). *V. himalayana* had maaliol (1), valeranone (9), kessane (10), and α -kessyl acetate (5) as major compounds, and *V. pyrolaefolia* contained patchouli alcohol (2) and valeranone (9) as markers⁶ (Fig. 1). Besides above, other important terpenoids identified in the genus *Valeriana* were bornyl acetate, δ -guaiene, α -santalene, β -gurjenene, α -guaiene, *allo*-aromadendrene, seychellene, viridiflorol (11), *epi*- α -muurolol, valerianol and kessyl glycol diacetate.

Based on an extensive NMR experiments, a novel oxygenated sesquiterpenoid epoxysequithujene (12) has been isolated and characterized in *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii*⁸. On the contrary, *Valeriana javanica*, a morphologically indistinguishable species, has been reported to possess α -kessyl acetate (5; 36.2%), patchouli alcohol (2; 10.3%), kessane (10; 6.8%) and valeranone (9; 3.2%)²³. Thus, the results conclude that the *V. hardwickii* and *V. javanica* have no similarity in their flavor compositions and this will consequently affect their use as medicine and flavour materials. Significantly epoxysequithujene is ca. 50% of *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii* essential oil and has not been noticed in any other *Valeriana* sp.

The volatile constituents isolated from roots and rhizomes of *Valeriana wallichii* DC. (*V. jatamansi* Jones) obtained from different sources, namely from a local

Fig. 1. Terpenoid markers in Indian Valerian.

market in Kathmandu (Nepal), from plants grown in The Netherlands and in Germany, and from commercially available material from several German importers have been investigated by GC and GC/MS (EI and NICI) analysis. The main constituents of Europe collection were α -santalene, *ar*-curcumene and xanthorrhizol while the Nepalese material and from the commercially available roots, except in one sample, patchouli alcohol as the main component²⁴

2.2. Non-glycosidic bicyclic iridoid epoxy-triesters (valepotriates)

Iridoids represent a large and expanding group of cyclopentan-(c)-pyran monoterpenoids, found as natural constituents in large number of plant families, usually but not invariably, as glucosides. The non-glycosidic iridoids or valepotriates are unique feature of the family Valerianaceae. Presence of a large number of small group of acylated iridoids, viz., the valepotriates associated with the sedative activity of valerian preparations have been isolated and reported previously from a widely explored species i.e., *Valeriana wallichii* syn. (*V. jatamansi*)¹³⁻²⁰. Two acylated iridoids, 7-acetoxy-5-hydroxy-1-isovaleroxy-11-[α -(isovaleroxy)isovaleroxy]-5,6-dihydrovaltrate (13)

and 7-acetoxy-1-[β -(methyl)-isovaleroxy]-11-isovaleroxyvaltrate (14) and were isolated for the first time from methylene chloride extract of the rhizomes of *Valeriana pyrolaefolia* Decne collected from high altitude meadows of Kumaon Himalaya. The structures (Fig. 2) were elucidated by their ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data interpretation²⁵. Moreover, there is no previous report on iridoid constituents of *V. pyrolaefolia*.

However, there are several reports which showed the isolation and characterization of new iridoid compounds from valeriana species. Recently, new acylated iridoids

Fig. 2. Valepotriates isolated from *V. pyrolaefolia* Decne.

called jatamanvaltrates (15-27) with some known valepotriates (28-36) (Fig. 3) have been reported in *V. jatamansi* syn. *V. wallichii*¹⁴. Some new iridoids, 11-homohydroxyldihydrovaltrate, 1-homoacevaltrate, 1-homoisoacevaltrate, 10-acetoxy-1-homovaltrate hydrin and 10-acetoxy-1-acevaltrate hydrin were reported from the

rhizomes of *V. jatamansi*¹⁵. An unusual iridoid bearing a C-10 chloro group and an oxo bridge, 1,5-dihydroxy-3,8-epoxyvalechlorine (37) together with valeritriates B and C and 8-methylvalepotriate were reported from the roots of *V. wallichii*¹⁷. Further, two new iridoid triesters isolated such as valeritriates A and valeritriates B have been characterized in *V. jatamansi* extract¹⁹.

3. Biological activity

3.1. Antidepressant and analgesic action

The valerian preparations are often used as mild sedative and sleep promoting agent or a substitute for synthetic sedatives in the treatment of nervous excitation and anxiety-induced sleep disturbances²⁶⁻²⁹.

Keeping the existence of chemotypes in view, antidepressant and analgesic effects of the extracts and essential oils of *Valeriana wallichii* chemotypes (patchouli alcohol and maaliol types) were undertaken to compare the changes in activity in relation to their chemical compositions. The patchouli alcohol chemotype extract demonstrated antidepressant effect and significantly increased the norepinephrine and dopamine levels in forebrain. It normalized behavioural and neurochemical alterations induced by forced swim test. The single administration of 40 mg/kg extract significantly reduced the immobility time without altering locomotor activity. Further, chronic administration of extract produced a significant dose dependent reduction in immobility^{26,27}. Efforts were made for elucidation of possible mechanism of analgesic action of *Valeriana wallichii* chemotype (patchouli alcohol) in experimental animal models using acetic acid induced writhing and tail flick model. Both extract and essential oil showed peripheral analgesic action and the effect being comparable to aspirin²⁸. The presence of terpenoids and valepotriates were noticed to be contributory to this activity of *Valeriana wallichii*. Preliminary acute toxicity assessment of both oil and extract performed show that lethal dose is much greater than the minimal analgesic dose which justify its pharmaceutical applications.

The results also suggested that both extract and essential oil of *V. wallichii* chemotype maaliol possess peripheral and central analgesic action. The peripheral antinociceptive action of essential oil being comparable to aspirin but weaker in case of central analgesic action. The extract, however possess weak peripheral and cen-

Fig. 3. Cytotoxic valepotriates isolated from *V. jatamansi*.

tral analgesic action. The presence of terpenoids and valepotriates may be contributory to this activity of *Valeriana wallichii*. LD₅₀ values of both the extract and oil are much greater than the minimal analgesic dose which makes the plant relatively safe and nontoxic to the animals. This makes the plant worthy for further studies to see whether it is the synergic effect or a particular compound responsible for antinociceptive action. The essential oil and dichloromethane extract of *V. wallichii* (maaliol chemotype) did not show any toxicity and behavioral changes in mice²⁹. When compared with our previous results of patchouli alcohol chemotype of *V. wallichii*, it was noticed that extract of patchouli alcohol was more effective at even the lower concentration than extract of maaliol chemotype in exerting peripheral analgesic effect, while oils of both the chemotypes exhibited comparable effect. Maaliol chemotype (essential oil and extract) inhibited central pain mechanism also but at higher dose while patchouli alcohol chemotype was devoid of central analgesic effect at the tested doses.

Valepotriates are iridoids found in variable amounts in Valerianaceae and might be among the bioactive compounds which confer anxiolytic properties to the *Valeriana* species.

3.2. Cytotoxic activity

Constituents of underground parts of three species such as *V. wallichii* DC. (*V. jatamansi* Jones), *V. officinalis* and *V. edulis* showed potent cytotoxic activity against GLC(4) a human small cell lung cancer line and COLO320, a human colorectal cancer cell line. Moreover, valtrate, isovaltrate and acevaltrate (dience class) showed cytotoxic nature with IC₅₀ values (1–6 μM) whereas didrovaltrate and IVHD (monoene type) showed less toxicity (2–3 fold less cytotoxic)³⁰. In addition, new acylated iridoids (15–36) isolated from *V. jatamansi* (syn. *V.*

wallichii DC.) were found to be effective against lung adenocarcinoma (A549), metastatic prostate cancer (PC-3M), colon cancer (HCT-8) and hepatoma (Bel7402) cell lines¹⁴.

3.3. Pharmacology

The commercial valerian preparations available worldwide are often used as mild sedative and sleep promoting agents and also as a substitute for synthetic sedatives in the treatment of nervous excitation and anxiety-induced sleep disturbances^{31–35}. The sedative activity of valerian based preparations has been tested both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. *In vitro* studies showed that the binding of valerian extracts to GABA receptors, adenosine receptors and barbiturate and benzodiazepine receptors^{36,37}. The hydroalcoholic and aqueous extracts possess affinity for the GABA-A receptors. The valepotriate, didrovaltrate showed some affinity for barbiturate and peripheral benzodiazepine receptors³⁶. The *in vivo* results revealed that the sedative action of the valerian may be due to the high glutamine concentration in the extracts. Moreover, glutamine can cross the blood-brain barrier, than taken up by nerve terminal and finally metabolized to GABA. Further, the addition of glutamine stimulates GABA synthesis in synaptosomes and rat brain slices. The spasmolytic activity of the valepotriates is due to the valtrate or dihydrovaltrate³⁸ which attacks on centres of the central nervous system and through direct relaxation of muscle³⁹.

4. Conclusion

The valerian extracts have been reported to depress central nervous system activity, however, the identity of the active constituents still doubtful. It has been also reported that neither the valepotriates, nor the volatile oil alone can be responsible for the sedative activity. Further, it was emphasized that some degradation products such as baldrinal (38) and homobaldrinal (39) of the valepotriates may also account for these activities (Fig. 4). Valerian probably has the potential for an anticonvulsant effect. Since the uncertain chemical composition and content of valerian preparations and their odor and taste, made it unlikely that they could ever prove satisfactory in widespread use⁴⁰. Insomnia affects approximately one-third of the adult population and contributes to increased rates of absenteeism, health care use, and social disabili-

Fig. 4. Degradation products baldrinal (38) and homobaldrinal (39) of valepotriates.

lity. Extracts of the roots of valerian are widely used for inducing sleep and improving sleep quality. The genus *Valeriana* is a good example of both negative and positive aspects of herbal drugs. The compositional differences along with instability of some of the constituents pose many questions required for drug standardization. Moreover, the markers responsible for activity suggest that this may cure a variety of conditions, which requires a sedative or tranquilizing effect.

Acknowledgement

Author (CSM) is grateful to the CSIR, New Delhi for grant of Emeritus Scientist Scheme and DST, New Delhi for the research grant in the form of the project.

References

1. P. J. Houghton, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1999, **51**, 505.
2. Y. Oshima, Y. Hikino and H. Hikino, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 1829.
3. J. T. Acharya, "Sushruta Samhita Commentary", Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sanasthan, Varanasi, 1992.
4. J. T. Acharya, "Charak Samhita", Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sanasthan, Varanasi, 1994.
5. C. S. Mathela, M. Tewari, S. S. Sammal and C. S. Chanotiya, *J. Essent. Oil Res.*, 2005, **17**, 672.
6. C. S. Mathela, C. S. Chanotiya, S. S. Sammal, A. K. Pant and S. Pandey, *Chem. & Biodiver.*, 2005, **2**, 1174.
7. C. S. Mathela, C. S. Chanotiya, S. Sati, M. Tiwari and S. S. Sammal, *Indian J. Traditional Knowledge*, 2006, **5**, 474.
8. C. S. Mathela, C. S. Chanotiya, S. Sati, S. S. Sammal and V. Wray, *Fitoterapia*, 2007, **78**, 279.
9. C. S. Mathela, R. C. Padalia and C. S. Chanotiya, *Natural Prod. Communications*, 2009, **4**, 1253.
10. S. Sati and C. S. Mathela, *Flavour Fragr. J.*, 2005, **20**, 299.
11. S. Sati, C. S. Chanotiya and C. S. Mathela, *J. Essent. Oil Res.*, 2005, **17**, 408.
12. S. Sati and C. S. Mathela, *J. Essent. Oil Res.*, 2006, **18**, 29.
13. H. Becker, S. Chavadej, P. W. Thies and E. Finner, *Planta Medica*, 1984, **50**, 245.
14. S. Lin, Y-H. Shen, H-L. Li, X-W. Yang, T. Chen, L-H. Lu, Z-S. Huang, R-H. Liu, X-K. Xu, W-D. Zhang and H. Wang, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2009, **72**, 650.
15. Y. Tang, X. Liu and B. Yu, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2002, **65**, 1949.
16. P. W. Thies, E. Finner and S. David, *Planta Medica*, 1981, **41**, 15.
17. S. Lin, Y-H. Shen, Z-X. Zhang, H-L. Li, L. Shan, R-H. Liu, X-K. Xu and W-D. Zhang, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2010, **73**, 1723.
18. L. L. Yu, C. R. Han, R. Huang, Y. P. Lv, S. H. Gu and Y. G. Chen, *Pharmazie*, 2006, **61**, 486.
19. L. Yu, R. Huang, C. Han, Y. Lv, Y. Zhao and Y. Chen, *Helvetica Chimica Acta*, 2005, **88**, 1059.
20. C. Bounthan, C. Bergmann, J. P. Beck, M. Haag-Berrurier and R. Anton, *Planta Medica*, 1981, **41**, 21.
21. R. Strachey, "Catalogue of the Plants of Kumaun and of the Adjacent portions of Garhwal and Tibet", Periodical experts (rep. ed.), Delhi, 1974.
22. V. Prakash, "Indian Valerianaceae : A Monograph on a Medicinally Important Family", Scientific Publ., Jodhpur, 1999.
23. R. Bos, H. J. Woerdenbag, H. Hendriks, H. V. Sidik, H. V. Wikström and J. J. C. Scheffer, *Flavour Fragr. J.*, 1996, **11**, 321.
24. R. Bos, H. J. Woerdenbag, H. Hendriks, H. F. Smit, H. V. Wikström and J. J. C. Scheffer, *Flavour Fragr. J.*, 1997, **12**, 123.
25. S. S. Sammal, PhD Thesis, Kumaun University, Nainital, 2005.
26. S. P. Sah, C. S. Mathela and K. Chopra, *J. Ethnopharmacol.*, 2011, **135**, 197.
27. S. P. Sah, C. S. Mathela and K. Chopra, *Phytomedicine*, 2011, **18**, 1269.
28. S. P. Sah, C. S. Mathela and K. Chopra, *Indian J. Exptl. Biol.*, 2010, **48**, 289.
29. S. P. Sah, C. S. Mathela and K. Chopra, *Pharmacologia*, 2011 communicated (Paper No. 144-PHARMA).
30. R. Bos, H. J. Woerdenbag and H. Hendriks, *Phytomedicine*, 1998, **5**, 219.
31. D. Shohet, R. B. H. Wills and D. L. Stuart, *Pharmazie*, 2001, **56**, 860.
32. J. Bruneton, "Pharmacology, Phytochemistry, Medicinal Plants", Paris, Lavoisier, 1995.
33. P. D. Leathwood and F. Chauffard, *J. Psychological Res.*, 1982/1983, **17**, 115.
34. P. D. Leathwood and F. Chauffard, *Planta Medica*, 1985, **2**, 144.
35. G. Balderer and A. Borbely, *Psychopharmacol.*, 1985, **87**, 406.
36. P. Morazzoni and E. Bombardelli, *Fitoterapia*, 1995, **66**, 99.
37. H. Wagner, K. Jurcic and R. Schaette, *Planta Medica*, 1980, **37**, 358.
38. H. Wagner, K. Jurcic and R. Schaette, *Planta Medica*, 1979, **37**, 84.
39. P. Houghton, *Pharmacy J.*, 1994, **253**, 95.
40. M. J. Eadie, *Epilepsia*, 2004, **45**, 1338.